
TAC. Open Syllabus and Open Tools to Train Young Data Makers

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An experimental learning experience for primary school children on how to produce and understand environmental data related to the urban environment through context-based tools, technology and methods.

Short Title	TAC project - Open Syllabus
Applicant	Serena Cangiano, SUPSI, LCV
Partners	SUPSI University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland SUPSI, Laboratory of visual culture (LCV) SUPSI, Institute of Earth Sciences (ISC) SUPSI, Institute for Applied Sustainability to the Built Environment (ISAAC) Municipality of Lugano / Lugano Living Lab Municipality of Lugano / School Institute Five schools in Lugano, with 7 classes and 7 teachers.
Duration	1 May 2020 - 30 April 2021

Summary of the results

The TAC project proposed an experimental educational program that focused on teaching students of primary schools how to produce and understand environmental data related to the urban environment. The goal was offering an innovative learning experience through sensors; the experience provided kids with environmental science and technology knowledge to trigger responsible behaviors. The project was stand alone, it was promoted by the Laboratory of visual culture and its FabLab (the lab dedicated to Open innovation at SUPSI) in collaboration with the new Lugano Living Lab established by the Municipality of Lugano and the School institute of Lugano with the broader goal of introducing education related to media and technology already in primary schools and facilitating the development of the digital citizenship in relation to the topic of environmental monitoring and data collection.

As planned, the TAC project delivered an open syllabus with the documentation of educational hands-on activities and a set of open tools that allow teachers to teach the use of environmental sensors and simplified electronics in class. An electronic kit, a mobile station and a web app helped students to understand the urban and natural environment through data science while developing more awareness on sustainability. From how sensors are used to how data is made public and interpreted, the educational experience was immersive and geared toward using technology as a means of learning the world of data, developing key 21st-century skills (collaboration and critical thinking), and understanding STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) teaching concepts.

The project transferred relevant research and technology skills from academia to citizens, through an interdisciplinary and collaborative action involving the municipality, the primary school teachers, the public engagement initiatives of the City of Lugano and the specialised companies Swisscom and Arduino.

Regardless of the extremely complex situation of the pandemic, the project produced results beyond its expectations, it activated a network of public and private stakeholders, it received a full endorsement from the City of Lugano with a supplementary support for the civil society engagement through an open workshop during the Digital Days 2020. The project has been presented as a case study of the IoT and society during the Swisscom days 2020.

Please refer to the links below for the documentation of the project and its tutorials.

Internal wiki

<https://www.notion.so/fablabsupsi/Progetto-TAC-Risorse-utili-bf622f0ef9954ad8896f46ea5fb0e95a>

Public repository of open source software and hardware

<https://github.com/FabLab-SUPSI/TACproject-devices>

[https://github.com/FabLab-SUPSI/TAC Device FW](https://github.com/FabLab-SUPSI/TAC_Device_FW)

Introduction

Technology literacy is one of the key 21st century skills necessary to face the challenges of the upcoming digital transformation and one of the main issue in educational contexts is how to train young students through approaches that are not focused only on traditional computer science teaching methods nor on the use of keyboards and mice, but on explorative and creative activities.

1.1 From big data to data makers. Framing the issues in technology education

Recent studies highlight how the impact of digital transformation could lead to the reinforcement of social issues. In the educational sector, the narrative of digitalization at all costs usually focuses on the introduction of new tools (VR sets, smart boards, etc.) or only on the didactic of computer coding to fill the gap in the tech job market. While there is an increasing demand for adapting the competences to the future jobs in fields such as data analysis, AI or robotics, school programs still struggle to bring computers in their classrooms. In this polarized landscape, initiatives and civic tech organizations raise the discourse on the introduction of an ecological and more social-driven perspective to the development of training formats addressing the digitization process. From citizen science to smart citizens actions, bottom-up innovation movements are proposing the use of technology for an empowering digital transformation in the education sector. At the same time, new learning models are trying to reconnect students with their societal context and personal development as citizens: connected learning, for example, proposes a learning model in which students pursue a personal interest or passion and link this learning and interest to academic achievement, career success, or civic engagement (2013). The principle of connected learning is also explored in the field of STEM education in which the community of educators and researchers pay attention to the opportunity to stimulate the development of key 21st skills such as creativity and complex problem-solving together with the mere digital literacy or technological skills (2010).

1.2 Data literacy through environmental sensing education.

A relevant field of application of the new approaches to civic tech is the environmental sensing and monitoring: low-cost sensors and web platforms allow non-experts to collect and interpret environmental data. Better environmental education through the use of data and technologies encourages people to behave more attentively and sustainably.

Civic environmental monitoring allows young people to get in contact with technology in an active way: they learn how electronics and sensors work in monitoring devices and how to participate as citizen scientists, or how to correctly read and interpret data in a graph.

Since the paradigm of IoT and connected devices is becoming more and more pervasive in our daily environment, this approach prevents future citizens from experiencing data in a passive way. This perspective demands innovative teaching approaches and tools to overcome the technological complexity and to simplify the learning experience through hands-on, inclusive, playful, and collaborative methods.

2. The project framework

2.1 A collaboration among the multiple stakeholders

The TAC (Technology Ambient and Competences) project aimed at allowing primary school children to produce and understand environmental data related to their urban environment through an innovative learning experience based on the use of sensors, and context-based tools. More broadly, the goal of the project is to introduce IoT and data literacy already at the primary school level, to facilitate the development of digital citizenship in relation to the topic of environmental monitoring and data collection.

The project started thanks to the collaboration among multiple stakeholders and it developed public and public partnerships:

- the Lugano Living Lab, digital innovation unit of the city of Lugano
- The school institute, the department that manages and coordinates all primary schools in the Lugano area
- Swisscom, the provider of Lora network in Switzerland
- Arduino, the company leader in open source educational electronics.

The project involved five elementary schools (six classes of pupils in fourth grade and one in fifth grade) and seven teachers, who also participated in a co-design and testing process in order to facilitate the integration of the project in the official school curriculum.

Driven by a multi stakeholder process, the project required to develop a preliminary research and mapping of the actor's needs:

- **the policy-making needs:** the municipality aimed to create a collaborative ecosystem of tools and a set of methods to connect with the civic society and engage it through empowering sensing technologies;
- **the school system needs:** the design process had to take into account the official curriculum guidelines. The guidelines require the introduction of technologies in the classroom only as a medium to learn something and not as a topic itself;
- **the teachers' needs:** the teachers' technology skills and expertise have been taken into account to define the professional development program on IoT and sensing technologies and to design the sessions to co-create the activities of the syllabus;
- **the students' needs:** as the project addressed students of the fourth grade (primary schools), it was important to map the knowledge and skills of kids between 9 and 10 years.

Fig. 1. The pedagogic framework of TAC project.

2.2 The pedagogic framework

The requirements for designing the project's pedagogic framework have been defined in collaboration with experts and the director of the School Institute and his team. The goal was to make the activities compatible with the official School Curriculum Plan. In the attempt of avoiding a technological focus, the framework puts at the center the student – as the main subject – and the competences, such as exploring reality and collecting information. The project pedagogic framework points at:

1. enabling students to develop skills by exploring the reality and collect information;
2. transferring the fundamental concept and processes of the scientific method;
3. developing skills related to the use of new technologies, and more specifically of sensors connected to the network, beyond their use in smartphones and videogames;
4. supporting environmental awareness in relation to citizens' behaviors and the urban context.

2.3 The tools

Following the mapping of the actors' needs, we focused on the analysis of the key user needs and the technical requirements. The latter has been defined through the study of existing solutions of DIY and citizen science environmental tools. By combining the actors' needs and

users' needs with the benchmarking of the solutions, we identified a series of requirements that helped us to guide the prototyping phase:

- real time data localization and monitoring
- portability and quick data access
- historical data visualization
- simplicity of use
- expandability
- embodiment

Those requirements lead to the development of the following ecosystem of prototypes:

- **The Node.** A localized device featuring a GPS module, a sound meter (microphone), a PM10 sensor, a humidity and temperature sensor and a light sensor. The Node serves the need of gathering real time and continuous data from a specific location and to enable the comparison among different locations. They feature high energy consumption sensors, the sound meter and the PM10, and for this reason they have been conceived to be installed in each school building.

- **The Kit.** A portable kit featuring a shape of a green character, with a humidity sensor, a temperature sensor and a light sensor. The kit has been conceived to enable groups of children to explore the environment and capture data in a full mobile set up. They are not localized in order to protect the privacy of the kids, and they have less sensors in order to make them easier to maintain in the scenario of a mobile learning experience. They are also cheaper: every school received five kits to use in team activities.

- **The Web App.** A web based application for tablets, featuring an interactive map and the data captured by the Nodes and the Kits. The data are visualized through interactive graphs.

Fig 2. The TAC node.

Fig 3. The TAC kit

Table of the devices

Device	Description	Iteration	Quantity
Nodes	GPS module sound meter (microphone) PM10 sensor humidity sensor temperature sensor light sensor Arduino MKR Lora Arduino ENV	1st: use of blocks and three sensors 2nd: integration of battery, noise sensor and PM10 sensor 3rd: Integration GPS module 4th: fix to GPS and battery	total: 15 Nodes 5 for the schools 10 to community test with a group of citizens
Students' kit	humidity sensor temperature sensor light sensor Arduino MKR Lora	1st: use of blocks to start the monitoring 2nd: integration in a custom PCB	30 kits
Web app	Heroku server Html Javascript Arduino API Swisscom client	1st: implementation of graphs 2nd: integration of communication system	1 version for tablet view

2.3.1 TAC technology ecosystem: Arduino and Lora network

The technological framework of the project is based on the combination of several technologies connected via a commercial Lora network. The brain of the node and the kit is an Arduino IoT MKR Wan. In the node, the Arduino board is connected to a second shield, the Arduino ENV. This shield features a set of environmental sensors that are directly processed by the Arduino MKR board and sent to the Lora network. From the Lora network, the data is stored in a web service that, via a set of APIs, talks to a web page, the TAC web app. This IoT infrastructure enables the connectivity of the devices without the need of using a sim card or Wi-Fi by reducing the complexity of use as well as the performance of the data storage and visualization.

Fig 4. The connectivity infrastructure and architecture.

3. The process

3.1 The co-design process

From October to December 2020, we organized a series of training involving a selected group of primary school teachers. The training has been offered within the official life learning program for teachers in Canton Ticino. The program has been designed with the following objectives:

- to transfer the didactic framework and the main mission and vision of the project;
- to transfer the design method to enable the teachers to generate the activities by always taking into account the main pillars of the didactic framework;
- to train the teachers on the technological concepts related to the paradigm of the internet of things and the use of Arduino based devices;
- to set up an open collaboration method to coordinate the pilots and the testing phases.

The training worked as co-design sessions because the teachers have been invited to actively participate in the definition of the activities rather than receiving a predefined playbook with a close structure of educational sequences. To guide the co-design sessions, we have defined a set of tools that have been distributed and used during the training to stimulate the collaborative co-creation process.

Fig. 5 Photo from the co-design session organized in October 2020.

The two tools were:

- the activity design canvas, a conceptual canvas featuring the key blocks to define all the elements of an activity;
- the activities map, a mind map with the three main themes generated during the first co-design session and the structure to create sub-activities or derivatives activities.

The problem or the phenomenon to study - which natural phenomena features the area where the school is located? - what problem the students can help solving?	Describe the activity - How do you introduce the TAC tools? - How can the students solve the problem tackled during the activity? - where does the activity take place? - how the collaboration among the students is managed or facilitated? -		
The competences What are the competences Es: searching specific data	The resources Only the kit The kit and the node The graph of the web app analog tools Boards or paper maps	Facilitation List the instructions that the students might need to complete the activity	Presentation What are the presentation modalities?

Fig. 6 The activity design canvas

The program scheduled 6 meetings with the teachers:

1. Introduction to the project's main topics, from IoT to environmental monitoring.
2. Introduction to the TAC tools ecosystem.
3. Co-design session to define a syllabus of activities.
4. Intermediate meeting to plan the activities' deployment in the classrooms.
5. Activity assessment. Evaluation of the technical aspects and the didactic activity. Planning of the technical support.
6. Evaluation of the experience.

The program included the contribution of three experts:

- Rachele Longhitano, researcher at Oasi Environmental Data Monitoring Lab of Canton Ticino;
- Massimiliano Cannata, head of Geomatic Sector - Institute of Earth Sciences of SUPSI;
- Roberta Castri, researcher at the Institute of Environmental Sustainability of SUPSI.

The presentations and all resources used during the trainings are accessible via the internal wiki at this link:

<https://www.notion.so/fablabsupsi/Formazione-docenti-ffd7fd3c7ddc4708b697e6f3e74aabfa>

3.2 The workshop with the citizens

Thanks to the support of the City of Lugano, we organized a hand-on workshop on the use of the TAC prototypes, with the participation of 15 citizens. The workshop took place during the Swiss Digital Days 2019 at Palazzo dei Congressi in Lugano. The goal was to open the methodology and tools of the project to a group of citizens and involve them in the testing phase of the prototypes, before implementing the activities in the classrooms. The workshop started the process of open development of the tools as well as of active engagement of citizens. The

workshop was held by Massimo Banzi, co-founder of Arduino (one of the project partners) and the documentation is available at this link. <https://youtu.be/KdXF9spawvQ>.

Fig. 7 Massimo Banzi (Arduino.cc) presenting the TAC node during the Digital Days (workshop with the citizens).

4. Open syllabus and evaluation of the pilot activities

The syllabus enables the activities to be scalable and reproducible and it supports the follow up of the project and the further development of its didactic framework. The open syllabus is a collection of didactic activities that have been conceived and tested in the classrooms. The version 0.1. of the syllabus is released at this link (<https://www.notion.so/fablabsupsi/Le-attivit-didattiche-Open-Syllabus-2aca4b65e6174f8b851dd49dc94e7b54>). This version includes ten activities conceived and tested by Isabella Reggi, teacher at the primary school of Ruvigliana. The other teachers have developed similar activities in their classrooms.

Fig. 8 Picture from the activity with the students (Elementary school in Besso).

Activity template

The activities are documented according to the following template:

- goal: what the activity wants to achieve;
- didactic sequence: how the activity is carried out;
- month, date: when the activity takes place;
- resources: what resources are used (digital, analog, materials, other monitoring devices);
- assessment of the format: what worked, what did not work.

5. Project outcomes: evaluation

The four months pilot program tested the didactic activities based on the tools and their performance in the classrooms.

Positive aspects

- the project's approach and methodology are original and fill the gap in the domain of data literacy development in young school students (elementary school grades);
- the project does not require prior knowledge of electronics and programming since the design of the tools pointed to be more inclusive towards teachers with different technology skills;
- the didactic framework fits the school curriculum, and it supports the further development of this approach and related contents;
- the design of the user-friendly interface (embodied in a character) made easier the integration of the technology in the classrooms;
- the possibility to use the kits in outdoor environments enabled the development of didactic activities that were more adequate to the didactics;
- the combination of different tools, the nodes and the kits, enabled the design of complementary and diverse activities that could be adjusted to the students' level and feedback;
- the tools and the didactic formats were adequate to the students' age and school grade;

- the choice to produce the case through 3D printing technologies allowed bringing also the concepts of DIY making in the classroom (one school could manufacture their own case).

Requirements and suggestions for the Follow-Up

- integrating teaching modules about technologies: in particular, a module could focus on data literacy by providing basic elements of coding and the electronics (Arduino board) for teachers. It is important to limit these sessions to avoid transforming the project in a bootcamp;
- expanding and modifying the kits with the help of the kids in co-design sessions that can involve them since the beginning of a new activity;
- adding features to the app, such as the possibility to download the historical datasets in readable formats (Excel spreadsheets);
- improving the user experience of the app to enable the students to use it at home or without the support of the teachers (the current prototype was supposed to support group activities with the facilitation of the teachers);
- improving the performance of the tools in order to support the use at home;
- designing a new series of training to empower the teachers and the students to become the maintainers of the tool;
- imagining how to train a group of parents to test their participation to the monitoring activities;
- integrating new modules in the teacher training (more time is needed to transfer all notions and competences).

COVID19 impact on the project schedule

Due to the COVID19 pandemic, we experienced a delay on the project plan in respect to the distribution of the hardware kits and the beginning of the pilots activities in the classroom. We distributed the first prototypes of the nodes in December 2020 and the kits in mid-February 2021. The ideated activities have been modified to fit the school calendar and deployed and tested starting from January 2021. The realization of video tutorials has been integrated to provide the technical remote support to the teachers. Three of six trainings have been carried out via skype.

6. Summary of the project results

	Description of the activities according to the project plan	Details and variations
√ Design and realization of the electronic kit, the mobile station, and the web platform (version 0.1 functioning prototypes).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • √ analysis of open source and low-cost solutions to create the electronic kit and the mobile station • √ prototyping of the kit: customization for the electronic kit and the mobile station • √ product and graphic design of the electronic kit and mobile station • √ development of the functioning prototype of the web platform • √ test and technology transfer <p>√ The budget included hardware of the physical kits (max 30 kit) and mobile station (max. 5, 1 for each school).</p>	<p><i>More than planned:</i></p> <p>+ The hardware and software was produced in collaboration with the company Arduino with the direct involvement of its co-founder Massimo Banzi</p>
√ The realization of the syllabus with the documentation of the educational activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • √ organization of co-creation sessions with the teachers • √ documentation of the activities in form of a digital document 	<p>√ The partner institutes of SUPSI ISAAC Institute of Sustainability Applied to the Built Environment and</p>

in collaboration with the primary school teachers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ✓ evaluation of the activities 	<p>SUPSI IST Institute of Earth Sciences Geomatics Section produced video tutorials and documentation for the training and syllabus.</p> <p><i>More than planned:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + The co-creation sessions with the teachers where organised through a series of meetings recognised as certified training + We involved also OASI (Osservatorio ambientale della Svizzera italiana) for the training and we included the documentation in the syllabus
✓ The testing of the TAC tools and activities in a pilot program distributed over one year in five primary school classes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ✓ the preparation of the activity • ✓ the teaching in class • ✓ the evaluation of the activity • ✓ the external support to the teaching sessions in class 	<p>✓ 5 schools involved.</p> <p><i>More than planned:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + 7 teachers involved with 6 pilots produced with an average of 15 children per class (around 100 kids involved).
✓ Documentation	<p>✓ To facilitate the distribution of the activities as well as the future replicability, the technical training for the teachers and all resources of the project (assembly guides, bill of materials, etc.) will be documented and released online in the form of video tutorials, digital guides, and instructables. This strategy will ensure the development of the project in cases of mandatory home schooling (i.e. pandemia emergency) and to support the adoption of easy to use distance learning solutions.</p>	<p>The City of Lugano living Lab organised a public workshop</p> <p><i>More than planned:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + The workshop involved a group of citizens in using the TAC project tools and to monitor its use and features. + The City of Lugano supported the production of a series of TAC station to involve a broader audience
Licenses and credits	<p>✓ The documentation and educational resources of the project is released under the Creative Commons attribution-share alike license (CC BY-SA all), unless differently stated. The licenses of the hardware components (Arduino modules and other sensors) are regulated by the manufacturer.</p> <p>✓ No patents have been generated and there are no other legal restrictions to the use and reuse of the project's contents and tools.</p>	
Involvement of the scientific advisor Lucio Negrini	<p>✓ To ensure that the activities are designed following the correct pedagogical approaches, the project will have a scientific advisor: dr. Lucio Negrini, researcher at Department of Learning SUPSI and head of CAS in Educational Robotics.</p>	

6. Licenses and credits

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manufacturer. No patents have been generated and there are no other legal restrictions to the use and reuse of the project's contents and tools.

Attribution: TAC Project, SUPSI & Lugano Living Lab, 2020-2021.

7. People

SUPSI LCV FabLab Iolanda Pensa, Serena Cangiano, Marco Lurati, Daniele Murgia

SUPSI, IST and ISAAC SUPSI: Massimiliano Cannata, Milan Antonovic, Francesca Cellina, Roberta Castri

Arduino.cc e Swisscom: Massimo Banzi, Andrea Scarinci

Lugano Living Lab: Rober Bregy, Elena Marchiori

Istituto Scolastico della Città di Lugano: Elena Beltrami, Patrick Kistler, Fabio Bocchino, Fabiano Gerosa, Marco Bettoni, Isabella Reggi, Roberto Milesi

8. Detailed budget

	Estimated					Reported	Difference
	Hasler Foundation	City of Lugano	In-kind SUPSI	In-kind Lugano	Total estimated	Total reported	
Material expenses	9800	2000			11800	11505,03	294,97
Serena Cangiano	14400				14400	14906,36	-506,36
Iolanda Pensa	1300	8000	5000		14300	12425,48	1874,52
Daniele Murgia	18000				18000	19507,40	-1507,40
Marco Lurati		2000			2000	2000	0
Francesca Cellina	1260				1260	1260	0
Massimiliano Cannata	5040				5040	5040	0
Graphic, photos					0	155,76	-155,76
Communication City of Lugano				15000	15000	15000	0
Total	49800	12000	5000	15000	81800	81800	0